

1 **Navigating the ‘fluid’ scholarly publishing environment for African academics**

2 *Enhancing the visibility, quantity and impact of African research*

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15 **Abstract**

16 In the dynamic landscape of scholarly dissemination, the traditional models of
17 academic publishing have been subject to substantive change. However, this has often
18 been met with several challenges including resource constraints, language diversity,
19 historical disparities, and infrastructure gaps. These challenges can slow down
20 academic progress and are especially pronounced on the African continent. To
21 navigate such a fluid environment strategically, academics on this continent must
22 enhance the visibility and impact of their research in order to achieve global recognition
23 to attract more international collaborations and research funding, as well as to facilitate
24 knowledge exchange, collaboration, and access to resources. Here, we explore the
25 impact of a fluid nature of scholarly publishing on the continent and provide an overview
26 of how researchers in Africa may navigate this dynamic environment. We explore
27 mechanisms for enhancing the visibility, quantity and impact of African research.

28 **Introduction**

29 Inadequate funding, restricted access to well-resourced laboratories, as well as a low
30 number of qualified researchers, are some of the reasons explaining why Africa
31 remains severely underrepresented in global research outputs (Tijssen and Kraemer-
32 Mbula, 2018). For example, approximately 3% of all COVID-19-related articles were
33 authored by African scientists, and just over 4% were focused on Africa (Kana et al.,
34 2021; Naidoo et al., 2021). These limited outputs imply that the knowledge deficit
35 regarding the effects of the pandemic on Africans remains substantial, and that, for
36 example, the relatively low number of deaths on the continent remains unexplained.
37 The knowledge deficit and the lack of studies on the long-term effects of the pandemic
38 is alarming when considering the fact that Africa has the second largest population of
39 any continent (Fonn et al., 2018). Nevertheless, only a fraction of the global research
40 publications is produced in Africa (Sooryamoorthy, 2022), and these are primarily
41 conducted in a handful of countries including South Africa and Egypt (Ali and
42 Elbadawy, 2021; Fonn et al., 2018). An array of challenges on the continent (e.g.,
43 political and economic instability, uneven distribution of research facilities, scarcity of
44 qualified researchers, and language barriers) limit research productivity in several
45 African countries, adding to the low representation in the global academy (Chu et al.,
46 2014; Conradie et al., 2018; Teng-Zeng, 2005).

47 In addition, sub-Saharan African countries contribute ~0.4% of Gross Domestic
48 Product (GDP) to research and development expenditure (Fonn et al., 2018). This is
49 well below the global average with OECD recommending that at least 1% of GDP is
50 spent on research. The lack of prioritization on science spending, combined with the
51 inadequate and uneven distribution of research infrastructure are further reasons for
52 the lack of research productivity in many countries on the African continent (Teng-
53 Zeng, 2005). The general lack of science policies articulating priority research areas,
54 the absence of competitive funding dedicated to research, limited opportunities for
55 collaboration, and the fact that highly trained academics rapidly progress to higher
56 levels of academia further exacerbate the situation.

57 Demographic predictions suggest that the number of Africans is likely to increase
58 substantially by 2100 (Gerland et al., 2014). In light of these substantial challenges and
59 the increasing population, Africa as a continent must strategically aim to meet its

60 potential and contribute significantly to global research outputs. These strategies
61 include enabling academic discussions, and tangible joint efforts, to enable increased
62 research productivity on the continent. This article therefore aims to highlight some of
63 the challenges limiting African research productivity, and vigorously advocates for
64 innovative solutions which must promote inclusiveness, equity and collaboration. By
65 supporting these efforts, African scientists can amplify their voices, disseminate their
66 research, and have their work recognized around the world.

67 **Challenges faced by African academics in traditional publishing models**

68 The current publication models, which include subscription-based journals, remain the
69 predominant mechanism for disseminating research outputs. Publishers that follow this
70 approach typically charge libraries, institutions, or individuals for access to publicly
71 funded research or databases on an annual basis. For many years, this model was the
72 primary model in academic publishing, particularly for established journals, and
73 typically includes strict copyright restrictions on article use and distribution. As a result,
74 these approaches are associated with high subscription costs, limited accessibility to
75 published research, and restricted readership (Laakso et al., 2016; Langham-Putrow
76 et al., 2021). African academics, particularly those from under-resourced universities,
77 are subject to access related difficulties. The fact that most research is locked behind
78 'paywalls' significantly limits scholarly endeavours. Specifically, most African scholars
79 are unable to carry out unrestricted literature surveys due to inadequate access to non-
80 open access journals. The inability to evaluate the latest research outputs, interferes
81 with the design of African studies, and may limit the ability to sufficiently consider data
82 generated by these scholars against the state-of-the-art studies.

83 The traditional publication model is subject to substantial criticisms globally. Well
84 documented criticisms include the misuse of journal metrics, particularly the Clarivate
85 Analytics journal impact factor (JIF) (Roldan-Valadez et al., 2019). The JIF is
86 disproportionately driven by a few highly cited articles and there has been concerns
87 that this metric has little to no correlation with the impact of individual articles published
88 by the journal (Abramo et al., 2023; Dougherty and Horne, 2022). However, the JIF
89 may fail to accurately measure the quality of any particular individual article due to the
90 inherent variability in citation counts (Dougherty and Horne, 2022), despite showing
91 the capacity to provide an overview of a journal's impact within a specific field.

92 Nonetheless, the use of the JIF for assessing individual articles and their authors
93 remains a topic of extensive debate (Waltman and Traag, 2021). This implies that while
94 certain statistical arguments question the JIF's accuracy at the article level,
95 acknowledging the variability in citation counts, it is equally important to acknowledge
96 that the JIF can provide meaningful insights under specific conditions (Waltman and
97 Traag, 2021). Thus, a balanced assessment should focus on a critical discussion of
98 the JIF's role in research assessments, taking into account both its limitations and
99 potential merits within specific contexts. Furthermore, it is critical to consider different
100 indicators and assessments, such as transparency, openness, and reproducibility
101 (Dougherty and Horne, 2022).

102 It is worth mentioning that many academics, including those in Africa, still value JIFs
103 when deciding where to submit their work (Roldan-Valadez et al., 2019). This may be
104 because the JIF is used by university managers and administrators as a key criterion
105 for evaluating promotions and tenure (McKiernan et al., 2019; Moher et al., 2018).
106 These factors may largely explain why the JIF remains influential on the evaluation of
107 scientific research and researchers in Africa's academic landscape. The downside is
108 that scholars that are unable to publish in high-impact factor journals may struggle to
109 meet requirements demanded by universities (McKiernan et al., 2019; Moher et al.,
110 2018). This may lead to delays in professional growth and further limit their capacity to
111 raise research funding. Therefore, the use of the JIF may create additional disparities
112 within research communities, especially those scholars in historically underprivileged
113 universities, which constitute the bulk of institutions on the African continent. Hence,
114 conventional methods of evaluating research contribute to research productivity
115 inequity. Thus, it is imperative for scholars in Africa to adopt a more proactive and
116 hands-on approach to effectively address these issues. While traditional publication
117 models have several disadvantages, the ability for African scholars to publish their
118 work without paying fees is certainly an enabler for disseminating research produced
119 on the continent. However, this model is currently facing challenges and the traditional
120 models are rapidly being replaced by open access publishing which often involve
121 paying a few. However, various models like green and diamond open access exist, and
122 these often not involve author fees.

123

124 **Understanding open access publishing and research visibility in Africa**

125 **The OAP model and related challenges**

126 Open access publishing (OAP) offers a promising alternative to traditional models as
127 it allows unrestricted access to research articles (Allen and Mehler, 2019). While the
128 OAP model promotes increased research visibility, a clear downside, particularly in the
129 case of APC (Article Processing Charge)-based gold open access, is that it shifts
130 publication costs to academic institutions and authors — it's worth mentioning that this
131 situation differs in green open access, where authors can share their work openly
132 without direct publication fees. Despite this, the OAP model rose to prominence over
133 the years and has since received great support from African scholars given that it
134 enables them to showcase their intellectual prowess (Strydom et al., 2022). The OAP
135 model is thus attractive to Africans in many respects, including boosting access to
136 research findings, wider readership, and compliance with funding agency
137 requirements, all of which positively influence one's career trajectory in academia
138 (Strydom et al., 2022). However, many scholars on the African continent face several
139 challenges including a lack of resources, typically disproportionately spread in favour
140 of some institutions.

141 While the shift towards open access is generally regarded as positive, especially in the
142 case of green open access, OAP has several downsides. Chief among these
143 downsides are APCs, which can be prohibitively high for most African scholars
144 (Strydom et al., 2022). These APCs are resulting in an uneven playing field in terms of
145 access to publishing opportunities, with pronounced adverse effects on historically
146 disadvantaged universities. In some cases, the costs of APCs may exceed the annual
147 salaries of postdoctoral fellows or research budgets and often the justification for these
148 charges is unsatisfactory. For instance, starting in 2021, making a paper open access
149 in Nature may be up to \$11,000, comparable to a postdoc fellowship in a typical South
150 African institution. Therefore, the goal of open access is not well balanced with the
151 financial realities of researchers and institutions in resource-constrained environments,
152 resulting in African scholars seeking more affordable alternatives. Of note, alternative
153 forms of open access, such as green and diamond open access, provide avenues for
154 disseminating research without imposing direct financial burdens on authors or

155 institutions, making them more viable options for researchers in resource-constrained
156 settings.

157 The rise of predatory publishing exploits the OAP model by charging lower fees often
158 accompanied by less stringent peer review with limited editorial oversight (Beall, 2017;
159 Shen and Björk, 2015). Predatory publishing has been a significant problem in Africa
160 for many years, with several studies investigating these practices on the continent in
161 research intensive countries including South Africa and Nigeria (de Jager and de Kock,
162 n.d.; Mouton and Valentine, 2017; Shen and Björk, 2015; Xia et al., 2015). These
163 studies have highlighted several intriguing trends. For example, Xia and colleagues
164 (2015) showed that young researchers who publish in predatory journals often have
165 few or no publication or citations. This is not surprising as unethical publishers may
166 appear legitimate to inexperienced scholars without a clear understanding of their
167 discipline specific publication landscape. The fact that some predatory stables offer
168 journals with high JIF further complicates the publication environment. Mouton and
169 Valentine (2017) presented some insightful strategies to effectively tackle these issues,
170 emphasising the involvement of senior academics. The challenge, however, is that the
171 African research landscape often has a dearth in senior academics, especially in areas
172 classified as scarce skills. This is particularly relevant as predatory journals lure
173 inexperienced academics by promising quick publication, and these authors are
174 sometimes lured into joining the editorial boards of these predatory journals and offered
175 substantial discounts on APCs. Consequently, such predatory tendencies increase the
176 presence of unreliable and misleading research. These predatory publishers result in
177 negative assessments of African scholarly outputs (Mills et al., 2021; Strydom et al.,
178 2022).

179 Predatory publishers may combine their efforts with the so-called paper mills, also
180 referred to as fake-paper factories, by accepting and publishing research papers
181 without rigorous peer review (Mills et al., 2021). Paper mills are “contract-cheating
182 organisations” that generate and sell pre-written or custom-written papers, to be
183 published by their clients (Byrne et al., 2022; Mills et al., 2021). This collaboration may
184 allow paper mills to rapidly generate academic content, which is then published in
185 predatory journals under an illusion of legitimacy. In turn, predatory journals may profit
186 from the fees paid by the authors. Although the collaboration between predatory
187 publishers and paper mills has received limited investigation, the existence of both

188 models highlights the need for increased awareness, scrutiny, and ethical practices in
189 academic publishing.

190 It is crucial to increase awareness of predatory publishing, and other unethical
191 practices, among African academics. We need to investigate methods to channel the
192 desire or pressure to disseminate research towards reputable publishing outlets that
193 prioritize research quality, integrity, and societal impact. These can include altering
194 reward systems, such as rewarding social impact instead of the journal impact (JIF),
195 support African journals embracing the OAP model in an ethical manner, and
196 promoting research ethics and integrity. Implementing these potential strategies may
197 reduce the extent of publishing in predatory journals, while considering the institutional,
198 economic and political contexts in each African country (Mills and Inouye, 2021). Given
199 the advantages and disadvantages of the OAP and traditional publishing models, it is
200 important to explore alternatives which could be applied on the African continent.

201 **The Equitable Open Access Publishing (EOAP) model as a viable alternative**

202 The African academic landscape has been subject to significant growth and
203 development, with increased contributions to the global knowledge systems. Some of
204 these contributions may be demonstrated by the rich and diverse indigenous
205 knowledge systems, which have been passed down through generations. To further
206 advance knowledge creation, dissemination, and accessibility, African institutions are
207 also exploring innovative models such as EOAP, while focusing on moderating the
208 risks and challenges discussed earlier. EOAP aims to promote fair and equal access
209 to scholarly research (Powell et al., n.d.; Vervoort et al., 2021), irrespective of financial
210 means or institutional affiliation. By virtue of its underlying principles, EOAP thus
211 recognizes the unique challenges faced by African researchers and researchers from
212 other developing nations (Powell et al., n.d.). By embracing EOAP principles, African
213 scholars can overcome the barriers imposed by traditional publishing systems and
214 ensure their work is accessible to a global audience. This inclusive approach may
215 ensure that research contributions are evaluated based on their merit rather than
216 financial resources, ultimately leading to a more equitable and impactful scholarly
217 publishing ecosystem.

218 Embracing the EOAP_{FI} and EOAP_{TD} model

219 As previously noted, EOAP, which we now distinguish as EOAP_{FI} to emphasize its core
220 principles of fairness (F) and inclusivity (I), aims to address the inequalities prevalent in
221 traditional subscription-based publishing. However, a question remains regarding the
222 academic landscape in Africa fully embracing the EOAP_{FI} model in its various forms
223 including gold, diamond, and green. Below, we advocate for the wide spread use of
224 preprints, preliminary versions of research papers which are made publicly available
225 on dedicated servers (e.g., bioRxiv, Research Square, Preprints.org, etc.) before or
226 simultaneously while undergoing peer review.

227 Preprints have emerged as a valuable addition to the publishing landscape (Puebla et
228 al., 2022). These preprints provide a broader range of options for disseminating
229 scholarly outputs. The advantages include opportunities for receiving direct feedback
230 from peers. With permissive policies, many journals allow researchers to submit
231 manuscripts that have previously appeared as preprints (Puebla et al., 2022). These
232 policies acknowledge the value of sharing work early and engaging with the broader
233 scientific community. Additionally, preprints are often indexed by platforms like
234 PubMed Central, Europe PubMed Central, and other bibliographic databases (Puebla
235 et al., 2022), ensuring their discoverability alongside peer-reviewed articles. However,
236 these platforms must adapt to effectively validate preprints as valuable research
237 outputs that enrich the broader scientific discourse (Waltman and van Eck, 2023).
238 Given the limited resources on the continent of Africa, we strongly advocate for policies
239 encouraging the use of preprint servers as a mechanism of sharing publicly funded
240 data.

241 Among the fundamental aspects that discriminates preprints from peer-reviewed
242 journal articles is earlier disclosure and immediate announcement of new discoveries
243 before peer review (Bourne et al., 2017; Ibragimova and Phagava, 2022). Therefore,
244 preprints embody the principles of the Early Open Access Publishing model, which we
245 consequently refer to as EOAP_{TD} (Early Open Access Publishing for Timely
246 Dissemination). This practice stands in contrast to the disclosure of discoveries through
247 peer-reviewed journal articles, which often undergo a prolonged review process
248 ranging from days to months, or even years (Vale, 2015).

249 **Cultivating a preprint culture in African research communities**

250 While the benefits of preprint articles may be the subject of several debates, their
251 significance and engagement has surged, particularly in the life sciences. This
252 increased significance was demonstrated during the early phase of the COVID-19
253 pandemic, where results were rapidly disseminated (Brierley et al., 2022; Fraser et al.,
254 2021). Preprints represent work which is shared before publication or peer review,
255 something which was central for sharing COVID-19-related discoveries. Preprints are
256 well aligned to a model which emphasizes the early release of findings i.e., EOAP_{TD} to
257 facilitate scientific engagement. In this way, preprints also promote EOAP_{FI} by allowing
258 for widespread dissemination of research findings, at no cost, fostering an arguably
259 more equitable publishing landscape. As a result, preprints effectively address issues
260 linked to the costs of publishing, as well as potential delays in publication due to
261 prolonged peer review processes. This implies that researchers can publish their work
262 without being subject to 'gatekeeping'. This is likely to facilitate the seamless inclusion
263 of knowledge from the African continent in the global scientific discourse.

264 However, because preprints are not peer reviewed, they have been subject to
265 considerable criticisms. For example, while there were several valuable contributions
266 to the scholarly literature during the early phase of the COVID-19 pandemic, several
267 dubious publications were published on preprint servers. These articles led to
268 considerable disinformation as they were reported as scholarly outputs in the
269 mainstream media. Therefore, we advocate for responsible preprinting practices if
270 these are to be widely adopted in Africa. These practices may include, for instance,
271 clearly labelling preliminary findings, ensuring timely updates which incorporate
272 feedback from peer reviews, and ensuring responsible media communication to
273 mitigate the risk of premature or misleading reporting of scientific results. Nevertheless,
274 there is some evidence that preprints are increasingly regarded as trusted sources of
275 information. This is due in part to increased open peer review of posted preprints, which
276 results in more robust scholarly contributions. The adoption of open peer-review
277 facilitates the transparent sharing of peer-review reports, and the authors are able to
278 respond to both peers and the public, ensuring more rigorous, inclusive, accountable,
279 transparent and high standard of peer-review while minimizing the potential unintended
280 biases and conflicts. Open peer review of preprints is largely facilitated by a number of
281 journal-independent preprint peer review services (e.g., PREReview, Open Research
282 Africa, Review Commons, Peer Community In, and eLife). Some of these services,

283 including Peer Community In and eLife, have been considered sufficient for meeting
284 the publication requirements for various PhD programs which require published
285 outputs as requirements for attaining doctoral degrees (Avisar-Whiting et al., 2023).
286 Several African-based preprint archives, including AfriRxiv and Open Research Africa,
287 as well as a number of regional servers like UnisaRxiv founded by the University of
288 South Africa, have embraced the preprint peer review model, indicating the increased
289 importance of preprints in Africa.

290 According to Invest in Open Infrastructure (IOI), a global initiative aimed at securing
291 funding and support for the infrastructure that underpins open scholarship and
292 research, the preprint ecosystem is not yet financially viable and relies significantly on
293 volunteer labour and in-kind donations (Penfold, n.d.). Open infrastructure - the digital
294 tools, systems, and services - facilitate the dissemination, sharing, and preservation of
295 scholarly outputs in an open and accessible manner. Such infrastructure includes
296 platforms for open access publishing, preprint servers, data repositories, and other
297 services which support the dissemination of scholarly outputs. African stakeholders
298 should consider partnering with initiatives such as IOI to better shape the future of
299 scholarly communication and research dissemination on the continent.

300 Preprints are a viable and valid avenue for research dissemination and may contribute
301 to significantly improving the visibility of African research. However, the use of preprints
302 remains substantially low in Africa, relative to other regions in the global north. Despite
303 this, several countries are beginning to recognize preprints as a valid form of scholarly
304 dissemination. For example, conducting a basic search using institutional affiliations
305 as keywords reveals a significant trend in preprint server utilization, with prominent
306 South African universities like the University of Pretoria, University of Cape Town,
307 Stellenbosch University, University of KwaZulu-Natal, North-West University, and
308 University of the Witwatersrand, showing an increase in preprint submissions during
309 the periods of 2014-2018 (63 submissions) and 2019-2022 (203 submissions).
310 Perhaps in future, preprints may become the most likely publishing option for achieving
311 the open science agenda, as some governments are beginning to demand immediate
312 and autonomous access to all scientific publications supported by public funds
313 (Hachigonta, n.d.; Tollefson and Van Noorden, 2022).

314 The low use of preprints in Africa may be attributed to a wide range of factors. These
315 factors include the lack of institutional support, policies and infrastructure, and
316 concerns over reputation and perceived lower quality of preprints relative to journal
317 publications. Entities such as the Africa Open Science Platform (AOSP) play a pivotal
318 role in promoting open science in Africa by providing a framework for collaborative
319 efforts. Such advocacy groups can fulfil a very important role by furnishing the essential
320 infrastructure, support, and advocacy required for enhancing preprint adoption in
321 Africa. However, the success of such an initiative hinge on several key factors,
322 including the level of engagement and collaboration among stakeholders, funding, and
323 community buy-in. Therefore, aligning actions and policies with preprint promotion will
324 foster a more inclusive scholarly publishing ecosystem. This will enable African
325 scholars to overcome the current systematic barriers, increase the impact of their
326 research, and actively contribute to the global knowledge system.

327 Other possible barriers to preprint adoption by African scholars include limited access
328 to technology, such as computers and internet connectivity. These may pose additional
329 challenges, particularly for researchers in remote areas, hindering the adoption and
330 use of preprints in Africa. In addition, cultural differences in norms and expectations
331 around scientific publishing may also influence the acceptance of preprints in the
332 continent. These norms vary across different countries and regions within Africa. For
333 instance, there may be a strong emphasis on publishing in reputable journals within
334 specific disciplines, as a measure of scholarly achievement and recognition. However,
335 due to hierarchical structures, senior researchers and established institutions hold
336 significant authority and influence. The fear of being 'scooped' by competitors may
337 greatly influence attitudes towards preprints, especially in Africa where competition for
338 resources is especially pronounced, and the pursuit of novelty and priority is crucial.
339 Therefore, concerns about being scooped may be a deterrent to embracing preprints
340 in Africa. However, since preprints come with a time stamp that authors can use to
341 establish their priority claims, they can therefore safeguard against the concern of
342 being scooped by others.

343 Additionally, awareness of the benefits of preprints is severely lacking in Africa. This is
344 due, in part, to the limited experience of how the preprint landscape operates. There
345 are efforts to heighten awareness of this landscape. For example, a non-profit
346 organization, Accelerating Science and Publication in Biology (ASAPbio), is working

347 with various stakeholders to address this knowledge gap. Each year, individuals
348 interested in preprints and other forms of open science are trained for ~6 months via a
349 comprehensive training curriculum that covers various aspects of preprints and open
350 science. This training includes focused sessions on preprint servers, preprint policies,
351 open peer review, and responsible preprinting practices. To provide a global
352 perspective on preprints and open research, participation in the ASAPbio Fellows
353 Program has consistently included African fellows since inception. This is, in fact,
354 contributing innovative ideas and discussions on preprints and open science in Africa.
355 Such initiatives will help to bridge the gap in the current understanding of preprint
356 trends and acceptance specifically between African researchers and the global preprint
357 community.

358 **Concluding remarks**

359 Rather than solely highlighting the deficits due to financial disparities between African
360 countries, we should focus on mechanisms for implementing solutions which will
361 promote equitable access to knowledge. Given the deficiencies of the existing
362 publication models, we advocate for the adoption of EOAP_{FI} and EOAP_{TD} (preprinting)
363 as concrete strategies for closing the current knowledge gap regarding African
364 research outputs. This will enable African academics to increase their contributions to
365 the global knowledge ecosystem. By embracing these two models, African scholars
366 can seize the opportunity to redefine scholarly publishing norms, challenge existing
367 power dynamics, and establish a more inclusive and equitable landscape. Therefore,
368 EOAP_{FI} and EOAP_{TD} provide avenues for African academics to have their voices
369 heard, their research disseminated widely, and their contributions acknowledged on a
370 global scale. However, raising awareness and increasing education on these models
371 will be key in achieving this goal.

372 In adopting EOAP_{FI} and EOAP_{TD}, governments and funding institutions must provide
373 infrastructure and financial incentives to facilitate the adoption of these models.
374 Adequate funding will also expediate access to state-of-the-art research facilities
375 including access to cutting-edge laboratories and equipment. This will enable African
376 researchers to conduct high-quality research. Moreover, to reduce the difficulties
377 associated with the current publication models and allow African researchers to share
378 their findings with a wider audience will require supportive policies including those

379 focused on research and publications. We further encourage more robust institutional
380 frameworks linked to research ethics and the establishment of compliance
381 mechanisms. These must be implemented to encourage open access publishing and
382 preprinting. In addition, African universities must take a proactive and pivotal role by
383 incorporating topics related to open access publishing and preprinting in their curricula,
384 particularly in terminal modules at third- and fourth-year. By so doing, these institutions
385 will increase student awareness of these issues, as well as build an academic culture
386 that supports innovative models of research distribution.

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